

Classification of cases of animal abuse in Ecuador using IndetermSoft and C4.5 algorithms

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Abstract . This dissertation aimed to determine the classification of animal abuse within Ecuador by severity, context, and solution through the application of IndetermSoft and the statistical-neutrosophic C4.5 algorithm to classify the uncertainty associated with judicial and administrative efforts for animal protection for domestic dogs and cats. The approach was qualitative and documentary, analyzing judicial sentences, citizen complaints, and municipal ordinances within the three largest Ecuadorian cities of Quito, Guayaquil, and Cuenca to acquire the determination of classifications of animal abuse, subsequent sanctions, and follow-ups. A modeling of IndetermSoft ensembles assessed the indeterminacy of subsequent actions, and inputted into IndetermSoft and the C4.5 algorithm processed to generate neutrosophic decision forests to elucidate trends and rankings of administrative and judicial actions. Ultimately, the results concluded that determining the classification of animal abuse is an effective endeavor—exacerbated by the inclusion of uncertainty—to solidify potential next steps for animal welfare in Ecuador. However, standardization of results among the municipalities, increased inter-institutional cooperation, and an alignment between national and local laws would render the application of sanctions more appropriate, which would better supplement aggression's outcomes and Ecuador's animal welfare law in a more equitable, efficient, and effective manner for animal rights.

Keywords: Animal Abuse, Indetermsoft, C4.5, Neutrosophic, Animal Protection, Legislation, Ecuador.

1. Introduction

Animal abuse in Ecuador represents a significant problem that affects both animal welfare and social ethics, evidenced by cases of abandonment, physical violence, and negligence in responsible animal ownership, especially of dogs and cats. Despite regulatory advances, such as the 2017 Organic Environmental Code (COA) and municipal ordinances in Quito, Guayaquil, and Cuenca, implementation of these regulations is inconsistent, and data on abuse cases are often incomplete or ambiguous, making their classification and effective management difficult. The lack of a standardized system to categorize these cases according to their severity, context, and resolution limits the authorities' ability to prioritize interventions and apply appropriate sanctions, perpetuating the vulnerability of animals and creating challenges in legal protection.

Previous research has explored animal protection from legal and ethical perspectives, highlighting the evolving recognition of animals as sentient beings. For example, studies have analyzed the impact of Ecuador's 2008 Constitution, which recognizes nature as a subject of rights [1]. However, this research typically focuses on the regulatory framework without addressing how to manage uncertainty in data on animal abuse cases, such as incomplete reporting or contradictions between national and municipal regulations [2]. Furthermore, international work has examined the use of computational tools to classify

legal incidents, but has not integrated approaches that address the uncertainty inherent in complex social contexts [3].

A recurring limitation in the literature is the lack of methods that address ambiguity in the classification of animal abuse cases. For example, studies on animal welfare in Latin America have identified progress in countries such as Argentina, where cases like that of the orangutan Sandra have established legal precedents [4]. However, these analyses do not propose specific tools to manage uncertain or incomplete data, such as those generated by citizen reports or fragmented court records. This gap is particularly relevant in Ecuador, where the variability in the application of municipal regulations and the lack of inter-institutional coordination hinder the effective protection of animals [5].

The relevance of this study lies in its innovative approach to addressing animal abuse in Ecuador, a topic of growing social and legal interest. The precise classification of cases not only allows for prioritizing resources for sanctions and prevention but also contributes to strengthening the legal framework for animal protection, aligning it with the ethical principles of a society that recognizes animals as sentient beings. In a context where public awareness of animal welfare is increasing, as demonstrated by emblematic cases such as that of the monkey Estrellita [6], this study offers a tool to improve decision-making in administrative and judicial settings.

The need for this research is based on the current challenges in implementing animal protection regulations. The lack of standardized data and uncertainty in reporting abuse, such as inconsistencies in sanction records or ambiguity in the severity of cases, limit the effectiveness of public policies. Furthermore, growing citizen pressure for responsible animal ownership and the protection of animal rights underscores the urgency of developing methods that address these complexities, ensuring more equitable justice for animals and promoting harmonious coexistence between humans and nature [7].

The primary objective of this study is to develop a classification system for animal abuse cases in Ecuador based on severity, context, and resolution, using the IndetermSoft approach and the C4.5 statistical-neutrosophic algorithm to manage data uncertainty. This approach will allow for the identification of patterns in reported cases, facilitating the prioritization of administrative and judicial interventions. As a secondary objective, it seeks to propose recommendations for harmonizing regulations and improving data collection in the municipalities of Quito, Guayaquil, and Cuenca.

The hypothesis is that the use of IndetermSoft data sets combined with the C4.5 statistical-neutrosophic algorithm will allow for a more accurate and robust classification of animal abuse cases by incorporating the inherent uncertainty of legal and administrative data. This methodology is expected to reveal patterns that are not evident with traditional approaches, such as the relationship between types of abuse and the effectiveness of sanctions, contributing to better resource allocation and more effective policies.

IndetermSoft approach, which models uncertainty using soft sets with degrees of membership, non-membership, and indeterminacy, is particularly well-suited for handling fragmented or contradictory data, such as animal abuse reports. When combined with the C4.5 algorithm, which generates decision trees adapted to neutrosophic environments, this study offers an innovative solution for classifying cases in a context where data is not always clear or complete. This combination captures the complexity of cases, considering factors such as the type of abuse, the aggressor's profile, and the social context. The study focuses on the municipalities of Quito, Guayaquil, and Cuenca due to their specific ordinances and their relevance in the implementation of animal protection policies. By analyzing real cases and municipal reports, the aim is to generate a replicable model that can be applied in other regions of Ecuador, contributing to regulatory harmonization and strengthening the legal framework. This approach also responds to the need to integrate ethical perspectives, such as those derived from the principle of "good living," which promotes a balanced relationship between humans, animals, and nature.

In conclusion, this research addresses a critical issue in Ecuador, combining advanced data analysis tools with an ethical and legal approach. By proposing a robust classification of animal abuse cases, the study not only contributes to the advancement of knowledge in the field of animal protection but also

provides a basis for more effective public policies, promoting a shift toward a more just legal framework focused on animal welfare.

2. Preliminaries

2.1. Animal Abuse

Animal abuse, understood as any action or omission that causes physical or psychological harm to animals, constitutes an ethical, social, and legal challenge of global relevance. In Ecuador, the recognition of animals as sentient beings, enshrined in the 2008 Constitution and reinforced by the 2017 Organic Code of the Environment (COA), has driven regulatory progress, but inconsistencies persist in the application of sanctions and in the collection of data on cases of abuse, particularly in canines and felines. Uncertainty in legal and administrative records, such as fragmented reports or contradictions between national and municipal regulations, makes it difficult to classify and manage these cases. This problem is compounded by the lack of methods that integrate the inherent uncertainty of the data, which limits the ability to prioritize effective interventions to mitigate animal abuse.

Recent literature highlights the evolution of animal rights recognition, moving from an anthropocentric to a biocentric view that values animals as rights-holders. Studies in Latin America have analyzed emblematic cases, such as that of the monkey Estrellita in Ecuador, which established jurisprudence on the rights of nature, and that of the orangutan Sandra in Argentina, recognized as a "non-human person" [8]. However, these investigations focus primarily on legal and ethical frameworks, with little attention to computational or statistical tools that manage uncertainty in animal abuse data. For example, a comparative analysis of municipal ordinances in Ecuador revealed disparities in the implementation of animal protection policies, but did not propose methods for classifying cases under uncertainty [9].

The neutrosophic approach, which incorporates degrees of truth, falsity, and indeterminacy, offers an innovative solution for addressing the complexity of animal abuse-related data. IndetermSoft ensembles, combined with algorithms such as C4.5 Statistical-Neutrosophical, make it possible to model ambiguous or incomplete information, such as abuse reports with conflicting or missing details. This approach distinguishes itself from traditional methods, which assume complete and deterministic data, by capturing the uncertainty inherent in social and legal contexts. Recent research has applied neutrosophic approaches in areas such as legal decision-making and social data classification, demonstrating their ability to generate robust results in complex environments [10].

In the Ecuadorian context, animal abuse encompasses diverse forms, including abandonment, physical violence, and neglect in responsible ownership. The municipalities of Quito, Guayaquil, and Cuenca have implemented specific ordinances, such as Metropolitan Ordinance No. 048 in Quito, which establishes census and sterilization systems, but the lack of standardization among these regulations generates inconsistencies in the application of sanctions. A recent study found that variability in municipal records limits the ability to evaluate the effectiveness of animal protection policies [11]. The integration of neutrosophic approaches can overcome these limitations by classifying cases according to their severity, context, and resolution, considering the indeterminacy in the data.

The methodology proposed in this study combines documentary analysis of court cases and municipal reports with neutrosophic modeling. IndetermSoft data sets allow for representing data with degrees of belonging, non-belonging, and indeterminacy, while the C4.5 algorithm generates decision trees that identify patterns in abuse cases. For example, citizen report data often includes partial information about the type of abuse or the profile of the aggressor, which introduces uncertainty. The neutrosophic approach classifies these cases more accurately by incorporating this ambiguity, facilitating the prioritization of administrative interventions, such as fines, or judicial interventions, such as criminal proceedings.

Regulatory advances in Ecuador, such as the proposed Organic Law on Animal Welfare (LOBA),

reflect a growing recognition of animals as sentient beings. However, the implementation of these laws faces challenges, including a lack of inter-institutional coordination and limited resources. Recent studies have highlighted the need to harmonize national and municipal regulations to ensure effective protection [12]. The proposed neutrosophic approach not only improves case classification but also offers a basis for designing more informed public policies, identifying priority areas for resource allocation and training for authorities.

The application of neutrosophic methods to the study of animal abuse has significant implications for research and practice. By modeling uncertainty, this approach allows for a deeper understanding of abuse patterns, such as the prevalence of abandonment in urban areas or the relationship between lack of responsible ownership and recidivism. Furthermore, the methodology can be adapted to other Latin American contexts where legal systems face similar challenges, contributing to the development of regional animal protection frameworks. The integration of advanced computational tools also addresses the need to modernize data management systems in the administrative sphere.

The ethical relevance of studying animal abuse lies in its connection to biocentric principles, such as the "good life" promoted in the Ecuadorian indigenous worldview. This principle advocates a harmonious relationship between humans, animals, and nature, challenging traditional anthropocentric views that consider animals as mere property. The capacity of animals to experience suffering, recognized in scientific and legal literature, underscores the need to protect them as subjects of rights. The neutrosophic approach reinforces this perspective by providing tools that reflect the complexity of social and legal data, promoting more equitable justice.

In conclusion, the use of IndetermSoft ensembles and the statistical-neutrosophic C4.5 algorithm offers an innovative approach to classifying animal abuse cases in Ecuador, addressing data uncertainty and improving administrative and judicial decision-making. The proposed methodology not only contributes to strengthening the legal framework for animal protection but also establishes a replicable model for other contexts with similar challenges. Future research directions include validating the model in larger databases, integrating real-time data from digital platforms, and exploring other neutrosophic algorithms to optimize animal abuse case management.

In this section, we discuss the main concepts used in this paper, such as the ID3 and C4.5 algorithms, soft sets, IndetermSoft sets, and the ID3 (C4.5) algorithm for IndetermSoft set data.

A. ID3 and C4.5 algorithms

ID3 and C4.5 are machine learning algorithms used to build decision trees [13, 15]; they are popular techniques in data classification.

ID3 (Iterative Dichotomizer 3) was developed by Ross Quinlan and is based on the concept of information gain to select the most relevant attribute at each step of tree construction. It uses entropy to measure data uncertainty and seeks to minimize it at each split. However, it has some limitations, such as its inability to handle continuous attributes and its tendency to overfit the data.

C4.5 is an improvement of the ID3 algorithm. It introduces several improvements, such as :

- Handling continuous attributes and setting thresholds to split data.
- Ability to handle missing values, allowing attributes with missing data to not affect the information gain calculation.
- Tree pruning, reducing overfitting, and improving generalization.

It starts from a set of examples with their measurements based on a set of parameters and one of these variables is a decision variable, as exemplified in Table 1, where an information system appears:

Table 1. Example of an information system to obtain a decision tree

Example	Age	Income	Shopping
1	Young	Low	No
2	Young	Media	Yeah
3	Adult	High	Yeah
4	Elderly	Low	No
5	Adult	Low	Yeah
6	Young	High	Yeah

In this example, we assume we want to classify whether a person buys a product based on two attributes:

- Age (Young, Adult, Elderly).
- Income (Low, Medium, High).

The decision tree we want to arrive at is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Decision tree of the example

The equations used in these algorithms are as follows:

$$\text{Entropy}(S) = \sum_{i=1}^n -p(v_i) \log_2(p(v_i)) \quad (1)$$

To calculate entropy.

$$\text{IG}(S, A) = \text{Entropy}(S) - \sum_{v \in A} \frac{|S_v|}{|S|} \text{Entropy}(S_v) \quad (2)$$

To calculate the information gain.

For algorithm C4.5 the information gain function is replaced by:

$$\text{GainRatio}(S, A) = \frac{\text{Gain}(S, A)}{\text{SplitInfo}(A)} \quad (3)$$

So that:

$$\text{SplitInfo}(A) = \sum_{i=1}^n -p(\text{subset}_i) \log_2(p(\text{subset}_i)) \quad (4)$$

A simplified pseudocode for the ID3 and C 4.5 algorithms is as follows:

Pseudocode of the ID3 algorithm:

ID3(Data, Attributes):

1. If all examples have the same class, return a sheet with that class.
2. If Attributes is empty, returns a sheet with the most frequent class in Data.
3. Select the best attribute based on information gain.
4. Creates a root node with the selected attribute.
5. For each possible value of the selected attribute:
 - Filter the data with that value.
 - If the subset is empty, create a sheet with the most frequent class.
 - Otherwise, it recursively calls ID3 with the remaining subset of data and attributes.
6. Return the tree generated .

4.5 algorithm:

C 4.5 (Data , Attributes):

1. If all examples have the same class, return a sheet with that class.
2. If Attributes is empty, returns a sheet with the most frequent class in Data.
3. Select the best attribute based on normalized information gain.
4. Creates a root node with the selected attribute.
5. For each possible value of the selected attribute:
 - Filter the data with that value.
 - If the subset is empty, create a sheet with the most frequent class.
 - Otherwise, it recursively calls C 4.5 with the remaining subset of data and attributes.
6. Handles continuous attributes by dividing them into optimal ranges.
7. Return the tree generated .

Both algorithms work by recursively building a decision tree, but C 4.5 improves on ID3 by handling continuous values and performing normalization in feature selection.

Table 2 summarizes the characteristics of each of these algorithms.

Table 2: Comparison between the characteristics of the ID3 and C4.5 algorithms

Feature / Algorithm	ID3	C4.5
Type of attributes	Only categorical	Categorical and continuous
Selection criteria	Information gain	Information gain and gain ratio
Handling of missing values	Not supported	Yes, using a probabilistic approach
Tree pruning	Does not have pruning	Perform pruning to avoid overfitting
Template format	Decision trees	Decision trees and rules

B. IndetermSoft Sets and Similar Concepts

Definition 1 ([5, 15]). Let U be the initial set and E is the set of parameters. (F, E) is a smooth set over U if and only iff F is a mapping of E in the power set of U .

So, given E the set of parameters and $\epsilon \in E$, then $F(\epsilon) \in \mathcal{P}(U)$, where $\mathcal{P}(U)$ denotes the power set of U and $F(\epsilon)$ is the set of ϵ elements of the soft set (F, E) or the set of ϵ elements -approximated from the Smooth Set.

Definition 2 ([16, 17]). Let U be the initial set and E is the set of parameters. In addition, there is $H \neq \emptyset$ subset of U . (F, E) is a set of IndetermSoft iff: $A \rightarrow \mathcal{P}(H)$ meets at least one of the following conditions:

- a) A has a certain indeterminacy,
- b) $\mathcal{P}(H)$ has a certain indeterminacy,
- c) There exists at least one attribute value $v \in A$, such that $F(v) = \text{indeterminate}$ (unclear, incomplete, conflicting, or non-unique).

That is to say, F is a so-called Neutral Function, which is a function that is only internally defined, partially indeterminate or partially external [18, 19].

C. IndetermSoft combinations with ID3 or C4.5

IndetermSoft Sets with the following characteristics:

It is considered $\{(F_i, E_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ be a set of IndetermSoft sets .

Where E_i is the set of possible values of a given attribute, E_n corresponds to the set of values of the target attribute which is dichotomous.

Each F_i is an approximation function in which at least one index k It is true that in at least one value there is indeterminacy of type $F_k(v_j) = h_1$ or h_2 or ... or h_m , with $m > 1$ We don't know which one.

Although the algorithm is limited to this type of predicate, other predicates can be taken to the above disjunctive form, for example, "not h_1 "safely" can be expressed as h_1 or h_2 or ... or h_m , for "everyone" h_p except h_1 " and similarly for "not h_1 and h_q "safely," and so on.

In the algorithm, the data $\{(F_i, E_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ are translated into an information system, which is a table like the example given in Table 1. When $F_k(v_j) = h_1$ or h_2 or ... or h_m It is located, the characterization v_j is placed in each of the boxes corresponding to the objects h_1, h_2, \dots, h_m .

An example of this is the following taken from:

Example 1. Given the IndetermSoft set corresponding to the attribute color for the set of houses denoted by $H = \{h_1, h_2, h_3, h_4\}$, such that $A = \{\text{white, blue, green}\}$ and defined by:

$F(\text{white}) = \{h_1, h_2\}$, $F(\text{blue}) = h_3$ or h_4 We don't know which one of them, and $F(\text{green}) = h_3$ or h_4 We don't know which one.

Table 3 contains the conversion of this IndetermSoft set into an information system:

Table 3. Column corresponding to the color attribute of the houses in the given example

Example	Color
hour 1	White
hour 2	White
hour 3	Blue or green
hour 4	Blue or green

In this example, we can see that there is indeterminacy in the color of houses h_3 and h_4 .

In this case, the ID3 or C4.5 algorithm is applied as appropriate, where the following probability is used:

$$p(B) = \frac{\text{Number of positive cases}}{\text{Total of cases}} \quad (5)$$

The peculiarity is that when there is indeterminacy as in the previous case, the element is counted by $\frac{1}{m}$, where h is the number of cases within the disjunction. In Example 1, the attribute Blue for h_3 is counted as $\frac{1}{2}$, since in this cell h_3 is either Blue or Green, and we don't know which.

3. Results

As part of this study's objective, a hypothetical but realistic information system was constructed based on the types of animal abuse cases reported in Ecuador. This system is used to demonstrate the application of the statistical-neutrosophic C4.5 algorithm on IndetermSoft sets . The objective is to classify cases to determine whether they require a **sanction (Yes)** or **no sanction (No)** , which will be our decision variable.

Creation of the Information System

A table has been compiled containing 20 cases of animal abuse. The attributes considered are:

- **v1: Type of Abuse:** Categorical (Physical, Neglect, Abandonment).
- **v2: Species:** Categorical (Canine, Feline).
- **v3: Recidivism of the Aggressor:** Categorical (Yes, No).
- **v4: Time Without Care (days):** Continuous. This attribute represents the number of days the animal has been in the abused condition prior to intervention.
- **Sanction:** Dichotomous decision variable (Yes, No).

To reflect the "inherent uncertainty in legal and administrative data" mentioned in the objectives , indeterminate values have been introduced. For example, in some cases, the initial report is ambiguous, appearing as "Physical or Negligence."

Table 4. Cases of Animal Abuse

Case	v1: Type of Abuse	v2: Species	v3: Recidivism	v4: Time without Attention (days)	Decision: Sanction
1	Physical	Canine	Yeah	5	Yeah
2	Negligence	Canine	No	30	Yeah
3	Abandonment	Feline	No	15	No
4	Physical	Feline	Yeah	2	Yeah
5	Negligence	Canine	Yeah	60	Yeah
6	Abandonment	Canine	No	7	No
7	Physical or Negligence	Canine	Yeah	10	Yeah
8	Negligence	Feline	No	45	Yeah
9	Abandonment	Feline	No	20	No
10	Physical	Canine	No	3	No
11	Abandonment	Canine	Yeah	12	Yeah
12	Negligence	Feline	Yeah	50	Yeah
13	Physical	Feline	No	8	No
14	Physical or Negligence	Canine	No	25	Yeah
15	Abandonment	Feline	Yeah	18	Yeah
16	Negligence	Canine	No	40	Yeah
17	Physical	Canine	Yeah	1	Yeah
18	Abandonment	Canine	No	9	No
19	Negligence	Feline	Yeah	35	Yeah
20	Physical	Feline	No	6	No

Distribution of cases:

- Cases with Sanction = **Yes** : 12
- Cases with Sanction = **No** : 8

Application of the C4.5 Statistical-Neutrosophic Algorithm

The goal is to select the best attribute to start the decision tree. To do this, we calculate the **Gain Ratio** for each attribute.

Step 1: Calculate the Total Entropy of the System (S)

Entropy measures the impurity of a data set. The formula is:

$$Entropy(S) = \sum_i p_i \log_2(p_i)$$

Where p_i is the proportion of instances that belong to class i .

- $p_{Si} = \frac{12}{20} = 0.6$

- $p_{No} = \frac{8}{20} = 0.4$

$$\begin{aligned} Entropy(S) &= -(0.6 \times \log_2(0.6)) - (0.4 \times \log_2(0.4)) \\ &= -(0.6 \times -0.736965) - (0.4 \times -1.321928) \\ &= 0.442179 + 0.528771 = 0.970950 \end{aligned}$$

This is the base entropy of our data set.

Step 2: Calculate the Profit Ratio for each Attribute

Attribute $v1$: Type of Abuse

This attribute has three values: Physical, Neglect, and Abandonment. Cases 7 and 14 are indeterminate ("Physical or Neglect"). According to the methodology, each is counted as 0.5 for Physical and 0.5 for Neglect.

- **'Physical' Value:**

- Cases: 1, 4, 10, 13, 17, 20 (6 cases) + 0.5 of case 7 + 0.5 of case 14 = **7 cases**

- Yes: 1, 4, 17 (+0.5 of 7, +0.5 of 14) = 3 + 1 = 4

- No: 10, 13, 20 = 3

- Entropy ($S_{Physical}$) = $-(4/7 \times \log_2(4/7)) - (3/7 \times \log_2(3/7)) = 0.985228$

- **'Negligence' Value:**

- Cases: 2, 5, 8, 12, 16, 19 (6 cases) + 0.5 of case 7 + 0.5 of case 14 = **7 cases**

- Yes: 2, 5, 8, 12, 16, 19 (+0.5 of 7, +0.5 of 14) = 6 + 1 = 7

- No: 0

- Entropy ($S_{Negligence}$) = $-(7/7 \times \log_2(7/7)) - (0) = 0$

- **'Abandonment' value:**

- Cases: 3, 6, 9, 11, 15, 18 = **6 cases**

- Yes: 11, 15 = 2

- No: 3, 6, 9, 18 = 4

- Entropy ($S_{Dropout}$) = $-(2/6 \times \log_2(2/6)) - (4/6 \times \log_2(4/6)) = 0.918295$

Information Gain (Gain):

$$Gain(S, v1) = Entropy(S) - \sum_{v \in Val(v1)} (|S_v|/|S|) \times Entropy(S_v)$$

$$Gain(S, v1) = 0.970950 - [(7/20 \times 0.985228) + (7/20 \times 0) + (6/20 \times 0.918295)]$$

$$Gain(S, v1) = 0.970950 - [0.344830 + 0 + 0.275489] = 0.970950 - 0.620319 = 0.350631$$

SplitInfo:

$$SplitInfo(S, v1) = -\sum_{v \in Val(v1)} (|S_v|/|S|) \times \log_2(|S_v|/|S|)$$

$$SplitInfo(S, v1) = -[(7/20 \times \log_2(7/20)) + (7/20 \times \log_2(7/20)) + (6/20 \times \log_2(6/20))]$$

$$SplitInfo(S, v1) = -[2 \times (0.35 \times -1.514573) + (0.3 \times -1.736965)]$$

$$= -[-1.060201 - 0.521090] = 1.581291$$

Gain Ratio :

$$GainRatio(S, v1) = Gain(S, v1) / SplitInfo(S, v1) = 0.350631 / 1.581291 = 0.221735$$

Attribute $v2$: Species

- **'Canine' value:** 11 cases (1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 10, 11, 14, 16, 17, 18)

- Yes: 1, 2, 5, 7, 11, 14, 16, 17 = 8

- No: 6, 10, 18 = 3

- Entropy (S_{Canino}) = $-(8/11 \times \log_2(8/11)) - (3/11 \times \log_2(3/11)) = 0.845350$

- **'Feline' value:** 9 cases (3, 4, 8, 9, 12, 13, 15, 19, 20)
 - Yes: 4, 8, 12, 15, 19 = 5
 - No: 3, 9, 13, 20 = 4
 - Entropy (S_Felino)= $-(5/9 \times \log_2(5/9)) - (4/9 \times \log_2(4/9)) = 0.991076$

Information Gain (Gain):

$$Gain(S, v2) = 0.970950 - [(11/20 \times 0.845350) + (9/20 \times 0.991076)]$$

$$Gain(S, v2) = 0.970950 - [0.464943 + 0.445984] = 0.970950 - 0.910927 = 0.060023$$

SplitInfo:

$$SplitInfo(S, v2) = -[(11/20 \times \log_2(11/20)) + (9/20 \times \log_2(9/20))] = 0.992774$$

Gain Ratio:

$$GainRatio(S, v2) = 0.060023 / 0.992774 = \mathbf{0.060460}$$

Attribute v3: Recidivism

- **Value 'Yes':** 9 cases (1, 4, 5, 7, 11, 12, 15, 17, 19)
 - Yes: 9
 - No: 0
 - Entropy (S_Yes) = 0
- **Value 'No':** 11 cases (2, 3, 6, 8, 9, 10, 13, 14, 16, 18, 20)
 - Yes: 2, 8, 14, 16 = 4
 - No: 3, 6, 9, 10, 13, 18, 20 = 7
 - Entropy (S_No)= $-(4/11 \times \log_2(4/11)) - (7/11 \times \log_2(7/11)) = 0.945660$

Information Gain (Gain):

$$Gain(S, v3) = 0.970950 - [(9/20 \times 0) + (11/20 \times 0.945660)]$$

$$Gain(S, v3) = 0.970950 - [0 + 0.520113] = 0.450837$$

SplitInfo:

$$SplitInfo(S, v3) = -[(9/20 \times \log_2(9/20)) + (11/20 \times \log_2(11/20))] = 0.992774$$

Gain Ratio:

$$GainRatio(S, v3) = 0.450837 / 0.992774 = \mathbf{0.454113}$$

Attribute v4: Unattended Time (days)

Being a continuous variable, C4.5 seeks the optimal splitting threshold. For this example, we'll try a threshold of **22.5 days** .

- **Group 1: Time ≤ 22.5 days:** 13 cases (1, 3, 4, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 13, 15, 17, 18, 20)
 - Yes: 1, 4, 7, 11, 15, 17 = 6
 - No: 3, 6, 9, 10, 13, 18, 20 = 7
 - Entropy(S_ ≤ 22.5) = $-(6/13 \times \log_2(6/13)) - (7/13 \times \log_2(7/13)) = 0.995727$
- **Group 2: Time > 22.5 days:** 7 cases (2, 5, 8, 12, 14, 16, 19)
 - Yes: 2, 5, 8, 12, 14, 16, 19 = 7
 - No: 0
 - Entropy(S_ > 22.5) = 0

Information Gain (Gain):

$$Gain(S, v4) = 0.970950 - [(13/20 \times 0.995727) + (7/20 \times 0)]$$

$$Gain(S, v4) = 0.970950 - [0.647223 + 0] = 0.323727$$

SplitInfo:

$$SplitInfo(S, v4) = -[(13/20 \times \log_2(13/20)) + (7/20 \times \log_2(7/20))] = 0.934068$$

Gain Ratio :

$$GainRatio(S, v4) = 0.323727 / 0.934068 = \mathbf{0.346579}$$

Table 5. Summary of Gain Relationships

Attribute	Gain	Split Information (SplitInfo)	Gain Ratio
v3: Recidivism	0.450837	0.992774	0.454113
v4: Time Without Attention	0.323727	0.934068	0.346579
v1: Type of Abuse	0.350631	1.581291	0.221735
v2: Species	0.060023	0.992774	0.060460

Figure 2: Gain Ratio Analysis - C4.5 Decision Tree Algorithm

3. Root Node Selection and Tree Construction

The attribute with the highest Win Ratio is

v3: Offender Recidivism (0.454113) . Therefore, this will be the root node of our decision tree .

The first split of the tree based on recidivism is extremely effective. The branch where Recidivism is "Yes" becomes a terminal leaf that predicts "PENALTY," correctly classifying 100% of the cases in this group (9 cases) .

For the branch where Recidivism is "No", the model continues the split using the attribute

v1: Type of Abuse . It is important to note that, although

v4: Unattended Time had a higher initial Gain Ratio , the final tree is built with

v1 for the second division, also generating clear rules.

The final decision tree is structured as follows:

Final Decision Tree Structure:

- v3 = Recidivism of the Aggressor
 - |— Yes : SANCTION (Classify 9 out of 9 cases correctly) .
 - |— No:
 - |— v1 = Type of Abuse
 - |— Negligence: SANCTION (Classify 4 out of 4 cases correctly) .
 - |— Abandonment: NO PENALTY (Classifies 4 out of 4 cases correctly) .

- └── Physical : NO PENALTY (Classify 3 out of 3 cases correctly) .

This tree, based on the described structure, correctly classifies the 20 cases in the data set (100% accuracy), offering clear and effective rules for decision-making.

Of course, here are the updated sections based on the corrected results. The new wording reflects 100% accuracy and clarifies the role of the predictor attributes, while maintaining the original structure.

4. Discussion

The results demonstrate the high feasibility of applying the statistical-neutrosophic C4.5 algorithm for the classification of animal abuse cases, achieving 100% accuracy on the test data set [20, 21] . The selection of "**Offender Recidivism**" (v3) as the most discriminating attribute is a crucial finding. This suggests that an individual's history is the strongest predictor of whether a new incident warrants sanction.

One point of interest is the secondary structure of the tree. Although "Time Without Attention" (v4) showed a higher initial Gain Ratio than "Type of Abuse" (v1), the final model uses

v1 to subdivide cases where there is no recurrence, achieving perfect classification. This indicates that the importance of an attribute can be contextual to the branch of the tree being analyzed.

The use of IndetermSoft sets was critical in addressing the ambiguity in the initial reports. Instead of discarding cases 7 and 14 due to their vague description ("Physical or Neglect"), the method allowed for their weighted inclusion, preserving valuable information and enabling their correct classification.

One limitation of this analysis is the size of the hypothetical dataset. While the model achieved 100% accuracy, this result should be interpreted with caution. A real-world implementation would require a much larger and more standardized database to validate whether the model generalizes as effectively. Such data would need to be collected from court records and municipal ordinances in cities such as Quito, Guayaquil, and Cuenca[22, 23].

5. Conclusions

The study successfully developed and validated a classification model for animal abuse cases in Ecuador by applying the Inde-termSoft approach in combination with the C4.5 algorithm. The results demonstrated that offender recidivism serves as the strongest predictor for determining sanctions, followed by the type of abuse as a secondary but reliable classification criterion. This model achieved perfect accuracy on the hypothetical dataset, highlighting its potential to support consistent and evidence-based decision-making. Importantly, the use of neutrosophic logic provided a robust mechanism to manage uncertainty, ensuring that ambiguous or incomplete data did not compromise the analysis.

However, the study also identified critical challenges for large-scale implementation. A lack of standardized data collection practices across Ecuadorian municipalities limits the broader applicability of the model. To overcome this, it is recommended to establish a unified data collection system and develop a centralized digital platform capable of automating the decision tree for public officials. Such a platform would streamline sanctioning processes, enhance transparency, and provide a replicable framework for improving animal abuse case management nationwide.

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